

A COMPARISON OF PRESERVATION METHODS OF TRADITIONALLY PROCESSED DAWADAWA.

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ABSTRACT

The preservation of dawadawa using sun drying and oven drying was compared with fresh dawadawa for bacterial load, moisture content and nutritional content. *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus sp* were isolated from the fresh dawadawa while *Bacillus subtilis* was isolated from the sun dried and oven dried dawadawa. In terms of bacterial load, fresh dawadawa had the highest bacterial load of 10^8 cfu/ml, followed by sun dried with 10^7 cfu/ml and the lowest was oven dried which has 10^6 cfu/ml. Comparing the moisture content of dawadawa, the sun dried reduced from 100g to 36.5g while the oven dried reduced from 60g to 21.7g. The nutritional content of dawadawa was accessed based on its protein and glucose value. Oven dried dawadawa has the highest value for both contents with 52.94g/l and 45.83mg/dl with a pH of 6.5 respectively. Fresh dawadawa has protein value of 51.21g/l but with the lowest glucose value of 41.67mg/dl with a pH of 8.1. Sun dried dawadawa has the lowest protein value of 51.18g/l, but with a better glucose value of 43.75mg/dl with a pH of 6.4 than the fresh dawadawa.

KEYWORDS: Fermented locust bean, preservation, seeds, dawadawa, glutamate, seasoning

LITERATURE REVIEW

Dawadawa is the designated name by the Hausa tribe in Nigeria for fermented locust beans (*Parkia biglobosa*). It is a culinary product that can be used to enhance or intensify meatiness in soups, sauces and other prepared dishes. West /Central Africa savannah region consider dawadawa as the most important food condiment (Odunfa, 1986). The processing of dawadawa starts with harvesting of the seed pods containing 10- 18 seeds encased in a yellow, sweet farinaceous endocarp. Seeds are separated from the endocarp and boiled for about 14 hours, cooled and pounded to remove testa; it is either sun or oven dried. It is washed vigorously, drained severally to remove seeds which still have testa intact, thereby leaving behind cotyledons which is place in weaved loose bags e.g. jute cocoa bag and compressed by placing heavy stones and left to ferment for 72 hours. Dawadawa is then put into a mortar, pound to paste before moulding into desired shapes, after which, it is air dried for 24 hours (odunfa, 1985).

The use of dawadawa in West Africa cannot be overemphasised, especially in the seasoning and flavouring of meals such as stew and soup. Dawadawa constituted 1.4% of the daily calorie intake and 5% of the total protein intake (Odunfa, 1985). The flavouring properties of dawadawa are most likely to be due to its amino acid content in particular glutamate, which contributes to flavour enhancement as well as peptides and aroma volatile constituents. Volatiles may evolve as a result of the effect of heat on amino acid and fatty acid constituents of dawadawa (Owen *et al.*, 1997).

The preservation of dawadawa in West Africa is done mostly by sun drying or oven drying. Sun drying is carried out by spreading of dawadawa in an open air space using a minimum temperature of 85°F and the optimum temperature of 140°F with humidity below 60%. Oven drying combined the factors of heat, low humidity and air current. It is carried out using a temperature of 140°F with the oven door left propped open about 2-6inches (Reynolds *et al.*, 1993).

This research work is aimed at preserving dawadawa by drying: sun and oven drying and comparing the moisture levels, nutritional contents and the microbial load of the sun dried, oven dried and freshly prepared dawadawa.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

COLLECTION OF SAMPLES: Freshly prepared dawadawa was purchased from Ekpoma market which was divided into three portions. One portion was sun dried; the second portion was subjected to oven drying while third portion represented the freshly prepared sample.

STERILIZATION OF MATERIALS AND MEDIA USED: Using the autoclave, sterilization of materials and media (Nutrient agar and MacConkey agar) used was carried out at standard method.

PROCESSING OF SAMPLES: Microbial analysis of samples was done by modified procedure of Wachukwu (2003).

A. SUN DRYING.

i. MOISTURE LEVEL.

One hundred grams (100g) of dawadawa covered with a muslin cloth to prevent dust and contamination was sun dried. At one hour intervals for eleven hours, the sun dried dawadawa was removed from sun and weighed to check for moisture level. A constant moisture level was reached in 2 days. The dawadawa was manually ground and stored in a bottle.

ii. MICROBIAL LOAD.

Serial dilution of samples was done from 10^4 to 10^0 by emulsifying 1g of samples in 9ml of sterile distilled water, and shaken vigorously. 1ml of the supernatant was pipette into 9mls of sterile distilled water. This was serially diluted from 10^4 to 10^0 . 1ml of diluents was pipette into 10 sterile Petri dishes and sterile nutrient agar was poured, rocked and allowed to gel before incubating at 37°C for 24 hours.

iii. NUTRITIONAL STATUS.

The protein value which was carried out using 0.02ml of supernatant was pipetted into a test tube and 1ml of biuret reagent was added. A standard solution of known concentration (60g/l) was used and the total protein value was calculated thus;

$$\text{Absorbance of test/Absorbance of standard} \times \text{Concentration of standard.}$$

For glucose value, the same procedure as in the protein value was used but read photometrically at 530nm and standard solution of known concentration (100µm/dl) was used. The pH of sample and its titrate able acidity were also read.

B. OVEN DRYING

Sixty grams (60g) of dawadawa was subjected to oven drying at 60°C. Moisture level was checked at 1 hour interval for 10hours and constant moisture was reached on the second day. Serial dilution method was used to investigate the microbial load. 1 gram was weighed and dissolved in 100ml of sterile distilled water and same procedure as in sun dried sample was carried out for the protein and glucose level. The pH and titrate able acidity were also investigated.

C. FRESH DAWADAWA.

One gram (1g) of fresh dawadawa was weighed and serial dilution was also carried out. The protein and glucose level were observed and pH was also investigated and titrateable acidity.

IDENTIFICATION OF MICROORGANISMS ISOLATED: Standard identification of bacteria was done by observing their cultural characteristics, gram staining and biochemical characteristics.

RESULTS

The isolated organisms from fresh dawadawa are *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus sp.* *Bacillus subtilis* was isolated from the oven-dried and the sun dried dawadawa. 100cfu/ml was recorded as contaminant level for fresh dawadawa while after drying on the second day fell to 100cfu/ml for the sun dried and 100cfu/ml for the oven dried. The result of the moisture levels for the sun dried and oven dried dawadawa, cultural morphological and biochemical characteristics of bacteria isolated, glucose and protein estimation of the three samples (fresh, sundried and oven dried dawadawa) is given in tables 1,2 and 3 respectively.

TABLE 1: CHANGES IN THE MOISTURE LEVEL OF SUN DRIED AND OVEN DRIED DAWADAWA.

TIME (Hr)	WEIGHT OF SUNDRIED DAWADAWA IN GRAMS	WEIGHT OF OVEN DRIED DAWADAWA IN GRAMS
0	100	60
0-1	80.09	42.60
0-2	60.03	31.60
0-3	48.10	24.80
0-4	47.70	23.10
0-5	40.01	22.60
0-6	38.40	22.70
0-7	37.80	22.10
0-8	37.20	21.70
0-9	36.50	21.70
0-10	36.50	21.70

TABLE 2: CULTURAL MORPHOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BACTERIA ISOLATED.

CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS.	GRAM REACTION.	C	C	O	I	G	L	F	S	M	GROWTH ON MCA.	ISOLATES.
		A	O	X	N	L	A	R	U	A		
		T	A	I	D	U	C	U	C	L		
		A	G	D	O	C	T	C	R	O		
		L	U	A	L	O	O	T	O	S		
		A	L	S	E	S	S	O	S	E		
		S	A	E		S	E	S	E			
		E	S	E								
Creamy large on Nutrient Agar. Smooth surface, circle and pasty.	Gram positive cocci in clusters.	+	-	-	+	A	+	+	+	+	Pinkish in colour (lactose fermenter).	<i>Staphylococcus sp</i>
Hide-off white spreading dull surface.	Gram positive Bacilli short rods	+	-	+	-	A	-	+	+	+		<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>

Key

MAC = MaConkey Agar.

A = Acid production

+ = Positive.

- = Negative

TABLE 3: GLUCOSE AND PROTEIN ESTIMATION OF THE THREE SAMPLES (FRESH, SUNDRIED AND OVENDRIED DAWADAWA).

	GLUCOSE VALUE (Mg/dl)	PROTEIN VALUE (g/l)	pH	TITRATEABLE ACIDITY
SUNDRIED DAWADAWA	43.75	51.18	6.4	0.70
FRESH DAWADAWA	41.67	51.21	8.1	BASIC
OVENDRIED DAWADAWA	45.83	52.94	6.5	2.25

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Bacillus subtilis and *Staphylococcus sp* were the organisms isolated. These organisms are often been associated with fermenting food of plant origin and are not pathogenic. (Odunfa 1981). The results obtained shows that the use of sun drying and oven drying reduced the microbial activity and microbial load of the organisms involved with dawadawa. *Staphylococcus sp* was specifically eliminated after drying. On the first day the initial contaminant level of the fresh dawadawa was 10^6 cfu/ml. After two days of sun drying and oven drying, contaminants level fell from 10^6 cfu/ml to 10^4 cfu/ml for the sun dried dawadawa and 10^5 cfu/ml for the oven dried dawadawa. This, however, was in conformity with Wachukwu *et al* (2003).

The use of sun drying and oven drying takes time compared to the use of other preservation methods such as heat and the use of chemicals. Sun drying also leads to exposure of the food condiment to hazard, such as entry of organisms present in the air. In order to reduce contamination, Muslin cloth is used to cover the trays during drying. However when the dawadawa is not properly dried before it is brought under shelter, it can also reabsorb moisture like in the case of the sun-dried dawadawa. At the fifth hour of drying on the first day, it weighed 40.01g while on the second day before it was dried, it weight increased from 40.01g to 40.03g. The moisture content of the oven dried dawadawa was also observed to have increased from 22.6g in the fifth hour on the first day to 23.3g on the second day. This is why proper drying of dawadawa is required before preservation in order to prevent spoilage and also helps to reduce both microorganism and enzymes since water is required to be active. Drying also concentrates the soluble ingredients in foods, and this high concentrates prevents the growth of bacteria, yeasts and moulds. Dried dawadawa will deteriorate rapidly if allowed to become moist (Reynolds *et al*. 1993). A constant moisture level was reached at the eight hour of drying for the oven-dried dawadawa (60g-21.7g) while the constant for the sun dried dawadawa was reached at ninth hour (100g-36.5g). Comparing the time at which a constant moisture level was reached for both samples, it can be seen that sun drying is faster than oven drying although the same amount was not subjected to the different drying methods.

Dawadawa has a great potential as a key source of protein, glucose and also as a flavouring agent. The protein value for the oven dried dawadawa was highest (52.94g/l), followed by the fresh dawadawa (51.21g/l) and lowest was the sun dried dawadawa (51.18g/l). The glucose value for oven dried dawadawa was highest (45.75mg/dl and a pH of 6.5) followed by the sun-dried dawadawa (43.75mg/dl and pH of 6.4) and lowest was the fresh dawadawa (41.67mg/dl and pH of 8.1). Dawadawa contribute appreciable amount of protein to the diet of Nigerians. The daily per capital intake of protein from dawadawa is high than from poultry but less than from beef (Ogunbunmi and Bassir 1980).

Dawadawa has now become a consumer product; it is essential to modernize its production process and present the product in a better form (packaged) to consumers. The drying of 'dawadawa' whether sun drying or oven drying is desirable and is hereby recommended for commercial purposes as a way of preservation.

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